

18. The use of biochar as co-feedstock in anaerobic digestion: Effects on digestate separation performance

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Introduction

Anaerobic digestion plant operators seek ways to improve profitability while maintaining environmental sustainability. One potential approach is using biochar as a co-feedstock. Studies suggest that biochar can enhance anaerobic digestion by improving microbial activity, pH buffering, and adsorbing inhibitory compounds, leading to increased biogas production and reactor stability (Devi and Eskicioglu, 2024). However, results vary, and further research is needed to understand biochar's full potential as part of anaerobic digestion value chains.

On-farm digestate separation is commonly used to facilitate the handling of solid and liquid fractions. Enhancing this process could improve the overall efficiency of digestate management. In addition, producing manure-based biochar and using it in digesters promotes circular use of nutrients and carbon, aligning with circular bioeconomy goals. Additionally, biochar may reduce greenhouse gas emissions and contribute to carbon sequestration, making it an environmentally promising option (Verdi et al., 2024). In this study, the aim was to examine the use of horse manure-derived biochar as a co-feedstock in a digester processing cattle slurry and grass biomass. The focus was on its impact on digestate separability and the broader benefits of integrating pyrolysis and anaerobic digestion for regional manure management.

Methodology

Horse manure was pyrolyzed in a small-scale mobile unit at 350–550 °C for 3.5 hours. Prior to the experiments, the resulting biochar was ground. Laboratory-scale 5 L digesters were used to co-digest horse manure-based biochar with cattle slurry and grass biomass. Biochar was added at 0% (control), 1%, or 3% of the fresh mass of slurry and grass. During digestion and sample collection, the organic loading rate (OLR) was gradually increased from 4.5 to 7.8 kgVS/m³d by adjusting the share of grass feed, while process parameters were continuously monitored, confirming stable operation throughout the collection period. Digestate was separated into solid and liquid fractions using sieving (2 mm) and centrifugation to assess the effects of biochar on mass separability, total solids (TS), and nutrient distribution. Centrifugation was carried out using a Lemitec MD centrifuge at (10,000 rpm, differential speed 200 rpm, weir disc 52).

Results and discussion

The pyrolysis of horse manure produced biochar with a TS content of 93%, while its carbon content was 68%TS. The addition of biochar as a co-feedstock in the digesters did not affect gas production, likely because the manure-derived biochar lacked characteristics favourable for enhancing biogas yield. This highlights the importance of biochar quality and its variability. The TS contents in the digestates were 8.3%, 9.1%, and 10.3% where the biochar additions (0%, 1%, and 3% as co-feedstocks to the reactors, respectively) resulted in increasing TS.

Separation of the digestate into solid and liquid fractions depended on the TS of the digestate. Sieving and centrifugation produced more liquid fraction with digestate having the highest biochar addition (3%), suggesting better particle degradation in the digester due to biochar addition. Compared to the control, biochar additions also resulted in 2.5 and 8.4% higher TS removal in the centrifuged solid fraction (with biochar additions of 1 and 3%), showing that more digestate TS was captured than what was added with the biochar. The centrifuged solid fraction had a high TS content (22%), compared to the control (15%). Results on nitrogen and phosphorus separability are still pending.

The tested concept promotes regional circular material use. Horse stables facing manure management challenges could supply pyrolyzed manure to local farm-scale digesters, which, in turn, may benefit from the improved digestate solids separation.

Acknowledgements

The study is conducted under BioKanta-project, which is funded by the Regional Council of Häme from the European regional development fund (ERDF).

References

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